

Full-text study exclusions

The following trials were excluded during full-text screening¹⁻³⁴.

1. Berger AA, Syed Z, Ryan L, et al. Superior Block Length and Reduced Opioid Use with Dexmedetomidine and Dexamethasone regional block versus plain Ropivacaine: a retrospective trial. *Orthopedic reviews* 2022;14(3) doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.52965/001c.31921>

Wrong study design

2. Chapman BC, Shepherd B, Moore R, et al. Dual adjunct therapy with dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine in transversus abdominis plane blocks reduces postoperative opioid use in colorectal surgery. *American journal of surgery* 2021;222(1):198-202. doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.amjsurg.2020.09.027>

Wrong study design

3. Chinese Clinical Trials Registry. Ultrasound-guided Quadratus Lumborum Block for Postoperative Analgesia in hip arthroplasty. <https://trialssearch.who.int/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=ChiCTR1800014295>, 2018.

Wrong comparator

4. Chinese Clinical Trials Registry. Effects of intravenous dexamethasone with or without dexmedetomidine on analgesic duration after knee arthroscopic surgery: a prospective, randomized, controlled, triple-blinded trial. <https://www.chictr.org.cn/showprojEN.html?proj=45142>, 2019.

Ongoing

5. Chinese Clinical Trials Registry. Dexamethasone combined with dexmedetomidine in the prevention of postoperative nausea and vomiting in patients with breast cancer: a prospective randomized controlled trial. <https://trialssearch.who.int/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=ChiCTR2000032943>, 2020.

No block

6. Chinese Clinical Trials Registry. Dexamethasone combined with dexmedetomidine as adjuvants of ultrasound guided transversus abdominis plane block in postoperative analgesia: a double-blind randomized controlled trial. <https://www.chictr.org.cn/showprojEN.html?proj=61074>, 2020.

Ongoing

7. Chinese Clinical Trials Registry. Effect and Safety of Dexmedetomidine and Dexamethasone as Adjuvant for Ropivacaine in Local Wound Infiltration for Post-Operative Analgesia in Lumbar Spine Fusion: a Prospective, Randomized, Double-blind, Controlled Clinical Trial. <https://trialssearch.who.int/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=ChiCTR2100042880>, 2021.

No block

8. Chinese Clinical Trials Registry. Ultrasound-guided thoracic paravertebral block with ropivacaine combined with dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine on chronic pain after thoracic surgery: a randomized controlled trial. <https://trialssearch.who.int/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=ChiCTR2200055832>, 2022.

Wrong comparator

9. Chitneni A, Hasoon J, Urits I, et al. Synergistic Effects of Dexamethasone and Dexmedetomidine in Extending the Effects of Pectoral I and Pectoral II Blocks for Postoperative Analgesia Following Total Mastectomy with Lymph Node Dissection. *Clin Pract* 2021;11(2):190-92. doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.3390/clinpract11020027>

Wrong study design

10. Clinical Trials Registry India. Prevention of postoperative nausea and vomiting and reduction of analgesic requirement by use of dexamethasone, dexmedetomidine and combination of dexamethasone-dexmedetomidine. <https://trialssearch.who.int/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=CTRI/2019/08/020888>, 2019.

No block

11. Clinical Trials Registry India. Comparison of pain relieving efficacy of Dexmedetomidine, Fentanyl and Dexamethasone as an adjuvant to Ropivacaine in above the Collar bone Brachial plexus block (USG guided) when administered perineurally in adult patients undergoing upper limb surgery. <https://trialssearch.who.int/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=CTRI/2020/08/027358>, 2020.

Wrong intervention

12. Clinical Trials Registry India. Effect of combined use of two drugs dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine on duration of nerve block. <https://trialssearch.who.int/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=CTRI/2020/11/029153>, 2020.

On-going

13. Clinical Trials Registry India. To compare the ability to prevent Nausea and Vomiting by Dexmedetomidine versus its combination with Dexamethasone after surgery of the abdomen in adult patients. <https://trialssearch.who.int/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=CTRI/2021/07/035276>, 2021.

No block

14. Clinical Trials Registry India. efficacy of dexamethasone or dexmedetomidine as an adjunct to levobupivacaine in USG guided superficial cervical plexuses block in thyroid surgery. <http://www.who.int/trialssearch/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=CTRI/2021/04/033253>, 2021.

Wrong intervention

15. ClinicalTrials.gov. Adjuncts for Adductor Block: Dexamethasone, Dexmedetomidine, or Combination to Reduce Pain. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT03643822>, 2018.

Suspended

16. ClinicalTrials.gov. Caudal Epidural With Non Opioid Adjuvants in Lumbosacral Spine Surgery. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT04411329>, 2020.

No block

17. ClinicalTrials.gov. Intravenous Dexamethasone and Dexmedetomidine on the Analgesic Efficacy of Erector Spinae Plane Block. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT04767256>, 2021.

Ongoing

18. ClinicalTrials.gov. Transverse Abdominus Plane Block Study: <https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT05216055>, 2022.

Wrong comparator

19. ClinicalTrials.gov. Long-acting Parasternal Blocks for Analgesia After Cardiac Surgery. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT05191745>, 2022.

Wrong comparator

20. Coviello A, Posillipo C, Golino L, et al. Anesthesiologic management of pregnant women with SARS-COV-2 infection undergoing cesarean delivery. *Clin Exp Obstet Gynecol* 2021;48(3):628-30. doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.31083/j.ceog.2021.03.2446>

No block

21. Cui Y, Sun Y, Xia M, et al. Computerized Tomography Image Features under the Reconstruction Algorithm in the Evaluation of the Effect of Ropivacaine Combined with Dexamethasone and Dexmedetomidine on Assisted Thoracoscopic Lobectomy. *J Healthc Eng* 2021;2021:4658398. doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2021/4658398>

Wrong study design

22. Cullom C, Arnett Z. Quality of Analgesia at Twenty Four Hours after using Dexamethasone and Dexmedetomidine as a Perineural Adjunct for Interscalene Brachial Plexus Block. *Anesth Analg* 2020;130:882-83.

Wrong study design

23. Gao X, Zhao T, Xu G, et al. The Efficacy and Safety of Ultrasound-Guided, Bi-Level, Erector Spinae Plane Block With Different Doses of Dexmedetomidine for Patients Undergoing Video-Assisted Thoracic Surgery: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Front Med* 2021;8:577885. doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2021.577885>

Wrong comparator

24. Herman J, Urits I, Hasoon J, et al. Synergistic effect of local dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine (Dex-Dex) in extending the analgesic effect of a transversus abdominis plane block prior to inguinal hernia repair. *J Clin Anesth* 2020;62:109703. doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinane.2020.109703>

Wrong study design

25. Irct20141209020258N. Comparison Dexametason and Dexmedetomidine and combination Dexametason and Dexmedetomidine for nausea and vomiting after laparoscopy cholecystectomy. <https://trialsearchwho.int/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=IRCT20141209020258N100> 2019

No block

26. Kwak H, Chang YJ, Lee KC, et al. Antiemetic efficacy of dexmedetomidine versus dexmedetomidine-dexamethasone combination in patients undergoing breast surgery. *Int J Med Res* 2019;47(10):5060-69. doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0300060519872031>

No block

27. Marrone F, Pullano C, Paventi S, et al. Dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine together as adjuvants of ropivacaine 0.15% for a brachial plexus block lasting 20 hours. *Minerva Anesthesiol* 2023 doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.23736/S0375-9393.23.17427-X>

Wrong study design

28. Munoz-Leyva F, Jack JM, Bhatia A, et al. No Benefits of Adding Dexmedetomidine, Ketamine, Dexamethasone and Nerve Blocks to an Established Multimodal Analgesic Regimen after Total Knee Arthroplasty. *Anesthesiology* 2022 doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1097/ALN.0000000000004326>

Wrong intervention

29. Noor NA, Urits I, Viswanath O, et al. Synergistic Effect of Perineural Dexamethasone and Dexmedetomidine (Dex-Dex) Prolong Analgesic Effect of a Preoperative Interscalene Block. *Cureus* 2020;12(7):e9473. doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.7759/cureus.9473>

Wrong study design

30. Panigrahi R, Roy R, Prasad A, et al. High dose dexamethasone offers better postoperative analgesia than dexmedetomidine when added to intra articular ropivacaine following knee arthroscopic surgery. *Anaesth Pain Intensive Care* 2016;20(3):273-77.

Wrong intervention

31. Rekei S, Naeimi AR, Mahmodiyeh B, et al. Comparison of the prophylactic effect of dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine and their combination in reducing postoperative nausea and vomiting in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *J Med Life* 2021;14(3):323-30. doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.25122/jml-2020-0030>

No block

32. Shamim R, Prasad G, Bais PS, et al. Ultrasound-Guided Suprainguinal Fascia Iliaca Compartment Block for Postoperative Analgesia in Patients Undergoing Hip and Femur Surgeries: A Retrospective Analysis. *Anesth Essays Res* 2020;14(3):525-30. doi: https://dx.doi.org/10.4103/aer.AER_9_21

Wrong intervention

33. Xuan C, Yan W, Wang D, et al. The Facilitatory Effects of Adjuvant Pharmaceuticals to Prolong the Duration of Local Anesthetic for Peripheral Nerve Block: A Systematic Review and Network Meta-Analysis. *Anesth Analg* 2021;133(3):620-29. doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000005640>

Wrong study design

34. Zusman RP, Urits I, Kaye AD, et al. Synergistic Effect of Perineural Dexamethasone and Dexmedetomidine (Dex-Dex) in Extending the Analgesic Duration of Pectoral Type I and II Blocks. *Cureus* 2020;12(9):e10703. doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.7759/cureus.10703>

Wrong study design